

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D1.4 – EOSC Sustainability best practice - revised

WP1 – Publishing FAIR RI data resources in EOSC

Lead Beneficiary: EMBL-EBI, Fraunhofer

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Contributing partner(s): EMBL, BBMRI-ERIC, MUG (LTD), UMCG (LTD), EATRIS, IMTM (LTD), IRFMN (LTD), FIMM (LTD), ECRIN, FZJ, ERINHA, INFRAFRONTIER, UNIMIB, INRA, UNIVDUN, Fraunhofer, HMGU, CERBM-GIE, FLEMING, UOULU, CIRMMMP, CERM (LTD), CSIC, VU, KNAW, UVEG, USMI, IMG, CNR, UNIMAN, VLIZ

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Contractual delivery date: **31 August 2023**

Actual delivery date: **29 November 2023**

H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2

Grant agreement no. 824087

Horizon 2020

Type of action: RIA

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	6
Project Objectives	6
Detailed Report on the Deliverable	7
1. Introduction	7
2. Methods	8
3. Discussion.....	8
Delivery and Schedule.....	9
Adjustments	9

Executive Summary

Sustainability of FAIR Life Science Resources and Projects: Lessons Learned from EOSC-Life Research Infrastructures

This report summarises the key findings regarding sustainable LS resources, based on experiences from the EOSC-Life project. A more detailed description of EOSC-LIFE sustainably experiences and lessons learnt is contained in a companion preprint¹ and published EMBO press article² for which this report will provide an introduction. In the publication, we describe organisational, technical, financial and legal/ethical challenges using lessons from 27 scientific projects selected via open calls, and the work of RI teams. We describe the efficiency of the EOSC-Life support model for sustainable FAIR data management and explore the complex sustainability needs for sensitive- and industry-related data resources. A set of recommendations, which can be applied to other EOSC and data infrastructure projects, are given. The impact of recommendations is evident in access statistics for the preprint and paper, as of November 28 2023 there were >2000 downloads of the preprint and >1,500 downloads of the publication.

Project Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following consortia-level objectives:

Objective 1: Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources for cloud use.

We have connected the RI data resources to EOSC via consistent, FAIR annotation practices (including provenance information) and cloud deployment and ensured that data publication meets ethical and legal requirements. Access to data and cloud services were underpinned by a shared federated authentication and authorisation infrastructure (Life Science AAI) including appropriate security for controlled data access.

Objective 3: Enable ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC.

We will achieve this objective by supporting user driven science (“user projects”) selected through open, excellence-based calls for access to our data resources and computational tools – mirroring established access models to RI facilities. We will kick-start the open call process by a pilot cohort of user projects, selected during proposal preparation by the Biological and Medical Sciences RIs based on their cloud maturity and usage of EOSC-Life resources and tools. This will be followed by open calls for user projects from different domains of life science, selecting projects with the highest potential to achieve ground-breaking discoveries by reusing integrated life science data via EOSC by external peer-review. We will create a group of BMS RI Data Experts, embedded in each partner RI, that support the user projects with in-depth data knowledge and cloud compute

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/8247376>

² <https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/embo.2023115008>

expertise. In addition, this group will ensure the sustainable and routine use of EOSC by the large user community of the BMS RIs.

Objective 8: Develop a technical sustainability strategy for data/data resources deployed.

The recommendations described in this strategy will address the experience and needs of the partner infrastructures and will also address the interoperability and data of services between infrastructures and their impact on sustainability strategies. Case studies will inform LS Research infrastructures at different stages of maturity on how sustainability can be achieved as an ongoing activity within and between LS Research infrastructures. This deliverable was conceived with a technical sustainability focus, and while this has been addressed, the wider sustainability context has also been considered (see Box 1) as technical sustainability can only be delivered if wider sustainability is achieved. The recommendations produced therefore have greater utility for the partners and the wider EOSC and life sciences communities noting, for example, the challenges related to personal health data.

The specific WP1 level objectives that are addressed in the deliverable are:

- a. Development of cloud compatible FAIR-compliant data resources (Task 1)
- b. Assessment of cloud feasibility of data/data resources and publication these repositories in EOSC for data reuse (Task 1)
- c. Advance the evolution of RI repository infrastructure for EOSC (sustainability) and the interfaces between the repositories supporting the RI demonstrators and open calls (Task 1)
- d. Provide consented data repositories and deployments (in support of WP4) (Task 1)
- e. Implementation of FAIR services and WP1 standards for RI data/data resources (delivered in WP6) (Task 2)
- f. Provide implementation strategies and exemplar implementations for cloud accessibility of RIs archival and added value data resources (Task 2)
- g. Integrate repository/data access with workflows (WP2) (Task 3)
- h. Develop a technical sustainability strategy for data/data resources deployed (Task 3)

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Introduction

To increase the impact of the deliverable and reach the widest possible audience, we have presented the EOSC-Life sustainability best practice findings in the form of a commentary paper under review in a scientific journal that also is available as a preprint³. The paper outlines the resources and services, and associated training and knowledge exchange, which have been supported and/or created within the EOSC-Life project. Within the publication we identify sustainability strategies that ensure long-term access to these resources and services, as well as their reuse, in a world where open-science policies increasingly dominate research and where data and software are shared and widely accessible. In addition, we clearly illustrate how EOSC-

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/8247376>

Life is positioned within the wider EOSC ecosystem, highlighting special considerations associated with life science resources. These considerations reflect the enormous diversity of studies, which range in scale and complexity from atomic-level results generated in structural biology to epidemiological analyses of a global pandemic.

2. Methods

In the publication we describe organisational, technical, financial, and legal/ethical challenges that present the main barriers to achieving sustainability regarding the reuse of life science data. The organisational challenges are associated with the non-aligned impact and reward mechanisms operating within academic organisations, where pursuing novelty and quickly following new trends are more likely to result in funding or tenure than establishing basic infrastructures that serve the wider community. The technical challenges are related to the need to promote awareness of how different data components, including identifiers, metadata schemata, vocabularies, and provenance, must all be FAIR, and to the need to develop effective implementation strategies. These components are often inconsistently applied, hindering data interoperability, and reducing opportunities for data reuse. The financial challenges derive from the fact that the data and services that are being generated are becoming increasingly complex, but the resources needed to perform basic operations, including curation, storage, computing, and long-term sustained access, are not scaled up accordingly. Ethical and legal challenges relate to, for example, GDPR regulations which ensure that individual citizens retain rights related to secondary use of their personal data which persist beyond the operational term of any one project or infrastructure.

3. Discussion

The work and experiences collected during EOSC-Life allow us to propose the following list of recommendations, which are further developed in the publication.

BE RECOGNIZED: Focus on strong credibility and recognition for the research done:

- [R1] Build with the experts.
- [R2] Publish, communicate, disseminate.

BE PRACTICAL: Demonstrating, practising, and reproducing permit better and sustainable adoption of research outputs:

- [R3] Demonstrate, not only tell.
- [R4] Plan training for immediate and future needs.
- [R5] Metadata makes FAIR.

BE READY: Sustainability requires agility and readiness to catch opportunities:

- [R6] Be prepared, agile and act timely.
- [R7] Curate **now**.

BE UNIFYING: Sustainability of products is based on clearly identified, recognised and motivated communities:

- [R8] Establish federated governance.
- [R9] Harmonise and integrate.
- [R10] Reward sustainability.

BE CLEAR: Inclusiveness and openness, as well as innovation, sustain communities:

- [R11] Be open **and** be inclusive.
- [R12] Treat innovation and sustainability independently.

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

